

Actor Role in Policy Implementation Disaster Risk Reduction

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Abstract

Disaster risk reduction is a comprehensive design in the development of a framework for disaster risk reduction with a proactive approach that aims to increase the capacity of governments, communities, the private sector in disaster management, both in situations of catastrophe does not occur, and in a situation there is a potential disaster.

Implementation of disaster management policies in Indonesia as stated in Law Number 24 of 2007 provides guidance on disaster management system with clear that success in disaster management is the responsibility of governments, and local governments. Because of the progress in addressing the wide scope of the disaster, the disaster management becomes the responsibility together. The involvement of actors in the implementation of disaster risk reduction policy, both actors the State, public, private and international agencies be crucial to success in disaster management. This study aims to describe and analyze the role of actors in the implementation of disaster risk reduction policy 2014 eruption of Mount Kelud in East Java. The study uses in-depth interviews with stakeholders involved in disaster management, the type of qualitative research and descriptive approach. The results showed that the involvement and collaboration between actors in the implementation of disaster risk reduction policy both actors the State, society actors, private sector and institutional actors on international, cooperative and coordinative in making a strategic step towards disaster risk reduction eruption of

Mount Kelud 2014 in East Java, so that the implementation of disaster management policies can be performed optimally. Recommendations generated in this study is, the portion of the role of state actors is still dominant in the implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction policies eruption of Mount Kelud, and has not resulted in a collaboration of an actor who balanced between state actors, civil society, private sector and NGOs, so that the necessary development of the role of the actor in the implementation of policies simultaneous and synergistic.

Keyword : Actor, Policy, Implementation, Disaster, Risk Reduction

Introduction

Disaster management system on lately experiencing a paradigm shift or approach, which has been using an approach that is responsive, that effort disaster management during and after the disaster, has changed and shifted his approach into a preventive approach, that is to preparations and adjustments made public in the face of disaster can reduce the risk of impact and greater damage in a disaster-prone areas and increase the ability to cope with danger (Paton & Johnston 2001). Preparation and adaptive attitude that made this community set out from their understanding of the disaster itself and the risks. This perception plays a major role in determining what they will do to prevent and avoid it (Coppola, 2006). Everyone has each other's perceptions about the risk of disaster. Slovic and Weber (2002) states that "differences in the understanding of risk will lead to discrepancies regarding risk reduction".

We must realize that understanding the disaster not only be understood in light of predictions of disaster that is certainty, but many disaster events in the natural world gives understanding to us that disasters can also unexpected (uncertainty), both from the time of the disaster, location and scale , Therefore the uncertainty of disaster management should be considered in determining policies on disaster. (Maarif. Journal of Disaster Management Dialog Vo.1 No.1 of 2010). Further assessment of the implementation of public policy as expressed by Meter and Horn (1986) that "a group of policy implementation, achievement of the objectives that have been outlined. As stated by Anderson (1979). That should be considered in the implementation of policies, namely: 1. Who is involved in the implementation, 2. The nature of the administrative process, 3. Compliance with suatu policy, 4. The effect or impact of policy implementation.

Besides the study of implementation of DRR policy coordination there is the problem that needs to fix and enhanced as presented by Pinkowski 2008 states that "Effective disaster preparedness and management require coordination and collaboration among public and private agencies and organizations on the local, state, national, and even international levels. The massive potential and actual disasters compel emergency planners and managers to improve upon existing disaster readiness and response plans and actions to minimize the devastating consequences".

Collaboration of an actor by Brown et al, 2001, called stakeholder is a person, organization or group with an interest in a particular natural resource. Collaboration role of actors involved in policy implementation as a

social event and arena of struggle. To clarify the public space where the actors play the role, then Renn (1992) sociologist who developed the theory of metaphor social arena (social arena metaphor) can be used to explain the events of an actor in disaster risk reduction policy.

Starting from the theory, then the actor or group of actors involved in the implementation of disaster risk reduction policy backgrounds and views and different interests to compete for and win his vision respectively. Even in the social arena metaphor theory of the actors has a motive, need, hope, encouragement, goals and objectives that move in articulating and fighting for his policy preferences or to respond to the policy preferences of others.

In this study, using the theory of policy implementation Lineberry (1978) and Anderson (1979) as the grand theory. As for analyzing the role of actors in the implementation of disaster risk reduction policies using a knife analysis using the theory Grindle (1980) as a middle range theory which states that implementation activities are affected by the contents of the policy and the policy context, further to an operational review, theory, using the theory Considine (1996) concerning policy actors, institutions, policies and policy instruments, Howlett and Ramesh (1998) that the actors in the process of the coalition as a subsystem of policies, within the framework of the advocacy coalition Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith (1993). As for assessing the management of disaster risk using theory Carter (2008) and Pinkowsky (2008). To complete the required theoretical study supporting the theory that the theory of stakeholders (stakeholders) from Brown, 2001), the theory of the social arena metaphor of Renn (1992), inter-regional cooperation on regional autonomy, and some journals associated with this research.

Disaster-hit people, making it the common and public problem, so it requires the presence of stakeholders to intervene collectively as making public administration domain. The pattern of collective interventions of stakeholders, public administration studies demanded to play the role and functions that its responsibility in disaster management. First public administration responsible resource use. Both public administration responsible to bear the costs to society. And third public administration responsible for committing public order and security.

Understanding of disaster management into a joint problem (common problem) requires mapping the structure of interaction and involvement of various parties who collaborate directly with the causes and victims of disasters. Parties involved have a variety of different roles and responsibilities. However, integrated disaster management system requires the synergistic interaction of all the actors. May not be charged to the government's disaster management course, neither let people fend for themselves to make efforts risking his life. (Kooiman, 1993).

Literature review.

In analyzing the implementation of disaster risk reduction policy 2014 eruption of Mount Kelud in East Java, using the perspective of public policy implementation. Implementation of policies not only bersangkutpaut the policy operational mechanisms into bureaucratic procedures but also issues related to the conflict, and bagaimana a policy decision was obtained by the target group.

Grindle in Abdul Wahab (1999) explains that the policy implementation process only memujudkan goals and those goals. This is a basic requirement for the implementation of public policy. Without the requisite conditions, the public policy is only a mere document.

Then Mazmanian and Sabatier (1981) also explains the meaning of policy implementation, namely: *“Understanding what happens after an actual program, enacted or formulated is the focus of attention of policy implementation, namely the events and activities that arise after the passing of state policy guidelines, which include both mengadministrasikannya efforts as well as to create due / real impact in the community or events”*.

Based on the above understanding, the technical aspects or the management (within an organization) is a means to realize the objectives set forth in public policy. The process of implementation of the new policy can be implemented if the implementation of the programs have been created, and funds have been allocated for the achievement of the policy objectives.

1. Actor Policies, Institutions and Policy Instruments Policy (Policy Actors, Policy Institution and Policy Instruments).

Actors Policy, institution policy and policy instruments have a very close attachment primarily on policy processes. Considine (1996) said that the institution is as steering policy mechanism, ie values

becomes a mechanism to policies created and forming a value strategy and learning or enabling. Controlling and regulating where each actor maintains its value is understood to control the values of others, and learning or enabling that actors learn the values of others (learning) as well as providing opportunities developing other values (enabling).

Howlett and Ramesh (2007) states, "policy actors in the policy process can mean the individuals or groups, where patterns of behavior involved in certain conditions as a policy subsystem". Both actors policy divide into four categories, namely: 1) Apparatus which has been selected (elected Officials) is the executive and legislative branches; 2) interest groups; 3) research organizations; and 4) the mass media.

The relationship between actors and institutions in the public policy process described Howlett and Ramesh (1998) as follows.

"The policies are made by policy subsystems (policy actors), which consists of the actors who participate directly in the policy process are included in policy networks, policy communities, the other executor-executor-these are actors existing policy on institutions within the structures of state and the organizations, community organizations and other organizations that exist in the international system. They may have been involved fully in the policy process, but some are made up marginally"

The essence of the opinion that the executors are actors policy in place at institutions within the structures and state organizations, community organizations and other organizations that exist in the international system.

"Institutions are referred to here is the policy of the state. He has the capacity to make and implement policy. Other institutional variables that affect the policy is the executive, legislative, and judicial branches of different social groups support from the community who joined in the institutional community organizations in formulating and implementing public policy in order to avoid the emergence of social conflicts. In addition, other groups that influence policy: interest groups are incorporated in the institutional business (economic actors or the business), labor organizations and organizations in the international system. (Howlett dan Ramesh, 2007)

2. A review of ACF from Paul Sabatier and Hank Jenkins-Smith.

Public policy is often considered to have two main characteristics, namely stability and change. By stability is meant that the processes of public policy is more incremental, referring to the past, and policy changes are only marginal. With the change meant that the contents of the policy changed fundamentally, government programs change dramatically.

Now that we are in an era where policy changes are more common than the stability and continuity of policy. Changes occur in various areas of public policy. Change already is an element that is more real than the processes of public policy rather than stability.

Based on the explanation, policy changes may occur in major or minor aspect. Major aspect of a policy subsystem includes a deep core beliefs and core policy beliefs. Policy core beliefs drawn from official statements about the values that are prioritized in policy, welfare who is considered in policy, authority relative of the government and the market, the proper role for the general public, political officials, civil servants, experts, as well as the causes of policy problems in the subsystem as a whole.

3. Theory of Metaphor Social Arena.

In acquiring theoretical insight comprehensive view of the public policy process as a social event and arena of struggle, then in explaining the position and role of the actors involved in the implementation of mitigation policies and disaster risk reduction eruption of Mount Kelud can be studied through the theory of metaphor arena social developed by sociologist Renn (1992). Starting from the theory, then the policy process should be understood as an social event and the arena of struggle, where the actor or group of actors involved in the implementation of disaster risk reduction policy eruption of Mount Kelud which has background rear and views and different interests to compete for and win his vision respectively. Early thoughts, before we examine in more detail in understanding the model of the social arena, there are two things that need to be underlined: first, this model does not regard the policy as an integrated whole, but rather as a series of negotiation efforts multilayered involving groups actors who directly participate; Secondly, in view of the role of the actor in the policy process, the theory of metaphor very selective social arena. econdly, in view of the role of the actor in the policy process, the theory of metaphor

very selective social arena. fact this model was only interested in the behavior of individuals or social groups that are deliberately directed to influence the policy.

4. The concept of disaster risk reduction

Time passed, the times evolve toward complexity so then came the new approach is more complex. This view emphasizes the hazards and vulnerability seta society's ability to face the dangers and risks of disaster. Natural phenomena can be a danger if it threatens humans and property. Furthermore, to learn more on disaster risk reduction policies, Nick Carter (2008) in his book "Disaster Management, A Disaster Manager's Handbook" to review disaster management in depth which is then supported by Pinkowski (2008) in his book "Disaster Management Handbook" to review about coordination when there is a disaster through early warning, as well as the actions to be taken in dealing with the handling of the risks of disaster reduction. In addition, the International Finance Corporation, World Bank Group in the title of his book "Disaster and Emergency Preparedness: Guidance for Schools" to review the school's involvement in disaster risk reduction management. And also from the UN-ISDR in many journals that discuss continuously all the problems related to the disaster.

Research methods.

This study uses qualitative research with descriptive approach. This research can describe the reality of the object of study and gives the meaning of the object studied. Even the opinion Straus and Corbin (2003) states that the research also reveal and understand something behind the new phenomenon known. Thus meaning a descriptive approach will contribute to the development of the theory of the object studied.

Qualitative data analysis Ian Dey (1993: 32) essentially rests on three related processes, namely: describing, classifying, and connecting. Describing the data obtained from the research findings, classifying the data that is to sort out which are relevant to the issues. While connecting the producing whole. As pointed out by Ian Dey that.

Results and Discussion.

Actor Role in Policy Implementation PRB eruption of Mount Kelud in East Java. Based on the findings in the field that the actors involved in the implementation of DRR policy eruption of Mount Kelud in East Java consists of four actors, namely; Actor Government Bureaucracy, the public actors, private actors, and actors International Non-Government agencies. In the field of empirical reality the involvement of many actors who work together and collaborate in the implementation of the Disaster Risk Reduction Policy eruption of Mount Kelud show cohesiveness and unity as well as the merging of all stakeholders in the same vision to save and avoid the disaster caused by the eruption of Mount Kelud

Remember and pay attention to disaster management needs with a growing magnitude, intensity, frekwensi and impact of disasters are so widespread, then the limitations of government in disaster prevention activities be less than optimal. Therefore the involvement of all the stakeholders becomes very important. Results of research on the case of the actor's involvement in the implementation of DRR policies eruption of Mount Kelud, find out about:

1. Identify Who are the actors involved:

Actors involved in the implementation of DRR policies eruption of Mount Kelud well as an individual, or group / institution in a community if the community governments, communities, businesses and NGO agencies. Individuals or groups have formed a network that we are familiar with the policy network to form a synergy of cooperation in the conduct of Disaster Management eruption of Mount Kelud. As the theory of advocacy coalitions Network (network advocacy coalition) policy Sabatier (1993).

The involvement of the actors in the implementation of policy disaster risk reduction (DRR) eruption of Mount Kelud depicted in the 3 pillars of disaster management in the implementation of policies mentioned there are four actors in the institutions involved in disaster management as described as follows:

Figure 1: Integration 3 pillars In the Disaster Management Policy Implementation DRR Source: Data are processed

In this case both central and local governments are still the basis for the policy agenda, although it must collaborate with multiple other policy actors. Although the government has nodality, authority, wealth and organizations, and local government is still a source of wisdom, but had to share the role with other actors such as NGOs, the private sector in the community and donors, where each other are interdependent both in information resources and penanggulangan financing in the disaster. The concept of network, partnership and kolaborasi have eroded the supposition that the more actors are involved is a limiting factor in the implementation of the policy, more and more actors increasingly complex communication and the greater the possibility of delays and obstacles in the implementation process. The limited capacity of actors and the more complex the policy of public affairs brings the trend of the actors establish collaboration, network or partnership. Sustainability of the collaboration needs for transparency and accountability, so that the actors involved understand the shortcomings and responsibilities in their respective duties.

Furthermore, to analyze the involvement of actors in policy implementation role of the actors in disaster management researchers tried using the analysis in strategic policy (Jastra) 2016-2019 BNPB, depicted in 4 quadrants of disaster management ie first quadrant known as Promoters, the second quadrant is referred to as latents, quadrant Defenders and the third called into four quadrants called Apathetic.

In the first quadrant, called quadrants Promoters, actor of bodies / organizations / institutions that have a strong influence includes having funding, program disaster, networking, personnel, facilities and infrastructure, and interest and commitment to support a high level of community disaster management. In the second quadrant, called latents actors who have a strong influence includes having funding, disaster programs, networking, personnel, facilities and infrastructure, but the interest and commitment to the communities lower their support in disaster management.

in the third quadrant, called Defenders, actors who have an interest and commitment to support a high level of community disaster management. But the actor has only weak influence because they do not have the funding, disaster programs, networking, personnel, facilities and infrastructure are not sufficient. While the quadrant into four so-called Apathetic, both actors who have influence and interest in the problems of disaster is very low, because their program is not relevant to its interests, even though they have significant funding. So its role is very limited at the moment just after the disaster.

As briefly mentioned quadrant models that investigators took from Strategic Policy National Board for Disaster Management (BNPB) 2016-2019 disaster relief, and then adjusted by the objective conditions in the field where catastrophic events happening in the field that describes the identification and calcification role of actors involved in the handling of the eruption of Mount Kelud 2014 assuming the parties involved in the disaster management activities as in the picture below:

Figure 2: Identification of the role of actors / stakeholders in disaster management.

Source: Strategic Policy National Board for Disaster Management (BNPB) 2016-2019

Based on a model to identify the role of actors / stakeholders in disaster management in the context of the handling of the eruption of Mount Kelud in 2014 the results of a study reported the following data:

In the first quadrant of the actors involved in the handling of the eruption of Mount Kelud consists of; disaster management agency area of East Java province, disaster management agency area Blitar district, Unit executor Kediri district now disaster management agency area, disaster management agency area Malang district, Indonesian Red Cross three District, the volcanology agency disaster mitigation and geology, the transportation bureau of communication and information, disaster response teams, Rescue team and Volunteers Department of Health, the Indonesian National Army, and the Indonesian National Police. In the second quadrant of the actors involved are the agencies involved in this case working unit, Public Works department, construction of public facilities, housing development agencies and Irrigation, local water companies, the state electricity company, Social Services, Office of population and civil registration, the Department of housing and settlement, the civil Service police Unit, financial watchdog and regional assets. While in the third quadrant actors involved include, universities, mass media, the Non-governmental organizations (NGO) and international non-governmental organizations. And last on the quadrant into four actors involved in the handling of the eruption of Mount Kelud is state-owned enterprises, local owned enterprises and private.

2. Portions role of actor involved in the implementation of DRR policies eruption of Mount Kelut 2014.

In the analysis of the proportion of the actors involved in the handling of PRB eruption of Mount Kelud in 2014, researchers tried to estimate the portion of each actor, which is estimated to provide an understanding to us that the role of the actor in each had a good portion of different interests and influence. This is because the role, duties and responsibilities attached to the duties and powers that have been charged to each agency / institution / agency different. So that the portion played also different.

Then the engagement portion actor's role in the handling of the eruption of Mount Kelud Disaster Risk Reduction can be described as follows:

Figure 3: Diagram Estimate Portion actor's role in the implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction Policy eruption of Mount Kalud 2014

Source: Data are processed researcher

Based on estimates of researchers revealed that the state / government in fact is no longer the sole actor in the management of Disaster Risk Reduction eruption of Mount Kelud, State / government as an actor and dominant and has competence in disaster management as well as have a great responsibility, there are at least three (3) important reason which can provide a strong argument that the State of dominant and competent:

First, from the stand point of public services, the state is obliged in disaster management for providing services to people affected by disasters. Second, the government as a regulator legally confirming that legally the state / government mandatory responsibility when residents suffered the effects of the disaster, and a third, state / government has a moral responsibility, because if a disaster occurs when not handled properly, then the State / Government the blame.

So the presence of the State has become an obligation and a duty that must be carried. While the presence of private actors, and the community as well as international institutions to support (Supporting agent) to provide reinforcement of success in handling the eruption of Mount Kelud. In certain situations on the stages / disaster cycle society actors and optimal instrumental in conducting disaster relief efforts such as during the pre-disaster, participate in training and workshops. At the time of the emergency response community actors involved to help and participate in the handling of the disaster, but the state becomes a stimulus they are engaged and more involved, because the state becomes the primary responsibility.

Conclusion.

The findings and analysis and discussion on the above results it can be deduced what the key points in the policy implementation of disaster risk reduction (disaster risk reduction) eruption of Mount Kelud, as follows:

Based on the findings in the field that the actors involved in the implementation of DRR policy consists of four actors, namely; Actor State (Government), the public actors, private actors, and actors International non-government agencies. In the field of empirical reality the involvement of many actors who work together and collaborate in the implementation of disaster risk reduction policy eruption of Mount Kelud show cohesiveness and unity as well as the merging of all stakeholders in the same vision to save and reduce the risk of disasters caused by the eruption of Mount Kelud.

a. Actor State (government) in accordance with the regulations of the disaster, that the actor country in this case disaster management agency area to center, while the Regency / City is the Regional Disaster Management Agency, Army, Police and bodies / organizations / institutions involved in this case the agencies involved in this case working unit local government.

- b. Actors from the public sector consists of several community care Kelud which members of the community "Anchor Kelud". Existing communities developed in the community there is a radio-based communications, from nature lovers from universities, and so forth.
- c. Actors from the private sector (business) in this regard entrepreneurs who set aside the company's profits in the form of Corporation Social Responsibility (CSR) for the use of helping and contributing during the pre-disaster, emergency response and post-disaster.
- d. Actors of international non-governmental organizations sector; which provides support both financial and physical support either at the pre-disaster, emergency response and post-disaster.

Based on exposure to multi-actor can be described that the interaction of actors, as well as the views Mazmanian and Sabatier (1979), the interaction of actors in policy implementation should synergistic, so that policy objectives can be achieved, even further to say that the implementation of the policy is a form of organizing activity which has been established by law and be a mutual agreement between the various stakeholders, actors, organizations (public or private), procedures and techniques synergistically driven to work together to implement a policy to a specific desired direction. Rationalization or reason behind such thinking is no more intended to attitudes, behaviors, and thoughts of all the stakeholders involved can be better controlled and precisely maintained tracks. Thus the goals and objectives of the overall policy program can be achieved optimally.

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